

BEUCITIZEN
BARRIERS TOWARDS EU CITIZENSHIP

EU Citizenship Teaching Packages for secondary school pupils

Document Identifier

D11.6 - Three teaching packages on European
citizenship for secondary education (14-16 year olds)

Version

1.0

Date Due

31/08/2016 (M40)

Submission date

24/04/2017

WorkPackage

WP11

Lead Beneficiary

UU

Dissemination Level

PU

Grant Agreement Number 320294
SSH.2012.1-1

Change log

Version	Date	amended by	changes
1.0	21.04.2017	Wieger Bakker	Final version submitted to coordination team

Partners involved

number	partner name	People involved
1	UU	Wieger Bakker
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this paper we present the outline of a series of five teaching packages for secondary school pupils in the age group of 14-16/17. These teaching packages all address a specific dimension of EU citizenship. More attention for EU Citizenship is relevant for several reasons. It first refers to the set of civil, political, economic and social rights that all citizens of EU countries possess in addition to the rights that come with their national citizenship. Secondly, it refers to the membership of a European political community in which each citizen of an EU country can participate actively; next to or intertwined with, being active in a local or national political community.

One of the conclusions from a comparative study of civic education in 7 EU-countries (D8.10 bEUcitizen), is that adolescents are hardly educated in what their EU citizenship rights are, nor are they trained in competencies to realize or enforce these rights. Parallel to this, young adults leave secondary school without being taught the civic and political competencies to participate in the variety of political communities on different levels they belong to.

EU citizenship is relevant when you stay in your country of origin and in the town you grew up in. For instance, in one's role as a consumer. Furthermore, political participation manifests itself on the local level in different forms. On the one hand, during elections: local, regional, national or European. On the other hand, in many forms of collective action by citizens who organize themselves in protest movements, around opinion leaders in the public sphere, interest groups and NGOs. Often when there is a European dimension, the action starts at the local level. For that reason, it is important that citizens both understand their rights and that a more lively European public sphere emerges. As a result, we choose to develop teaching materials for secondary school pupils that contribute to the EU dimension of their civic competencies.

With these teaching packages we do not intend to lobby for or create support for EU citizenship. Our goal is to make EU citizenship visible in a realistic way, showing concrete relevance not only for 'movers' but especially for those who stay at home; show how EU citizenship is directly related to one's daily life and how one can influence these choices.

After having outlined the goals, target group and didactics, in the appendix a summary of the five teaching packages are presented:

1. Getting my rights: Europeanization at home
2. Lobbying and getting in touch with the EU
3. Organizing our interest
4. Travelling around
5. Advising the EU in solving Global Problems

1. GOALS

The overall goal of these teaching packages is to teach secondary school pupils (aged 14 – 16/17) about EU citizenship.

With the teaching packages for secondary school pupils we want to focus on two aspects:

1. EU citizenship is directly related to your daily life and you can benefit from it.
2. Choices made on the level of the EU affect your daily life and you can influence these choices, together with others close to you, as the EU is only five or less handshakes away from any EU citizen.¹

With these teaching packages we pursue three concrete goals. We want the pupils:

- a) to discover what rights they have as EU citizens, both during their daily life at home, and when traveling around;
- b) to develop the necessary competencies to get access to, realise and/or enforce their rights;
- c) to develop the civic and political competencies to participate in the variety of political communities on different levels they belong to in order to make their voices heard in decision-making on all levels.

This implies that the teaching packages depart from the perspective of the secondary school pupil in his or her daily life and local habitat.

¹ The well known 'six degrees of separation' concept, originally formulated in one of his short stories by the Hungarian journalist Frigyes Karinthy in 1929, states that everybody in the world is six steps away from anybody else or less.

2. TARGET GROUP

The overall target group is secondary school pupils, aged 14 – 16/17, across the whole of the European Union.

All secondary schools throughout the EU should be able to effectively use these packages, and all secondary school pupils throughout the EU should be able to relate to the content of the packages.

This means that:

- The characters in the cases (which are part of the teaching packages) make for a broad representation of the secondary school pupils in the EU. There are diverse in their background, gender and age (within the age group of 14 – 16/17).
- The topics or issues in the packages are EU-wide, they are not connected to specific countries or regions.
- The topics and issues dealt with in the packages are 'real-life'. Secondary school pupils could actually encounter these topics and issues in their lives, or have encountered them.
- All the packages and materials are stated in English, as this is the most commonly used second language for secondary school pupils in the EU.

3. DIDACTICS

The teaching packages are designed according to the following requirements:

1. Flexible teaching packages that can be adapted to the needs and values of the different educational systems and the needs of the schools and teachers; no 'one size fits all';
2. The packages should be flexible enough to blend into existing teaching materials and content.
3. Relatively 'small' teaching packages, to be implemented in 30 to 45 or 60 minutes;
4. Focus on active experiential learning, blending games and simulations with the information and insights you need for these;
5. Interactive ways of working, using digital materials;
6. Using real life cases to show patterns and make dilemma's visible;
7. Staying away from, and being sensitive to 'propaganda';

In addition, the teaching packages focus on the following didactic issues:

- They aim at transforming the EU from something abstract and far away to something concrete, real and close to home.
- Invite the secondary school pupils to learn about EU citizenship in a playful manner, by presenting real-life situations they could actually encounter in their lives.
- They avoid jargon (even the word 'citizenship', which can be abstract) but at points introduce concepts which are 'filled' with meaning, by showing how a concept works out in the real world.

OUTLINE

Curriculum

The curriculum consists of 5 teaching packages. They all have the same standard outline (see next section), but they vary in topics, learning objectives and assignments. Together the packages form a coherent teaching curriculum, covering a broad spectrum of aspects of EU citizenship, training a broad set of knowledge, skills and competencies.

Teachers can use each of the 5 teaching packages individually as standalone lessons, but they can also teach several or all of them as a series, e.g. 1 daily lesson over a period of 5 days.

If they teach multiple packages, we suggest an order of teaching them. The rationale behind this order is the following: the packages start close to home and deal with very tangible issues. This in order to raise awareness that EU citizenship is something very real – not only when travelling abroad, but also when staying at home. The packages gradually move further away from home, and the topics become somewhat more abstract.

<i>Teaching package</i>	<i>Working title</i>	<i>Topic</i>	<i>Learning objective</i>	<i>Main character</i>	<i>Suggested order of teaching</i>
Getting my rights: Europeanization at home	Boris and his headphones	Consumer rights	Raising awareness of how the EU protects consumer rights.	Boris	1
Lobbying and getting in touch with the EU	Making the future work for us	Labour market	Understanding different levels of influence and policy making (local, regional, national, European)	Katrina	2
Organizing our interest	A multimedia centre in our town	(Popular) culture	Organizing different interests around a common goal.	Juan	3

Travelling around	A school trip with a twist	Mobility and travel (and care/education)	Learning about the rights for EU citizens that come with travelling abroad, education abroad and care abroad.	Vanja	4
Advising the EU in solving global problems on a local level	Clean air for all of us	Environment	Developing negotiation skills. Understanding that complex issues are dealt with at multiple levels within the EU.	Pierre	5

Standard outline of a single teaching package

The teaching packages are designed to be modular, so they can be adapted to the time available (see next section).

A package in its most complete and extensive form looks like this (the approximate time a specific segment takes is noted in parentheses).

1. General instruction (5 minutes)

The teacher tells the pupils:

What topic this lesson will be about.

What the learning objective is.

How long the full lesson will take and what parts it's made of.

2. Case pt. 1 (5 minutes)

There is a central character, a protagonist, to every package. In the appendix the characters are called 'Boris', 'Lucie', 'Juan', 'Vanja' and 'Nikolas'. This character is featured in part 1 and part 2 of the cases and in the assignments. The case is shown to the classroom through a 'motion comic' (a short animated movie (approximately 2 minutes)). The case presents a situation in which the central character finds him – or herself. The case ends with a problem, dilemma or question (typically: what would you do?)

3. Assignment 1 (10 minutes)

The assignment can take the form of:

A) quiz with closed and open questions, to be answered by the whole classroom

B) open questions and assignments

The quizzes and questions for the assignment are presented to the classroom by means of a PowerPoint presentation.

4. Informative segment 1 (5 minutes)

This segment provides some additional information following the case and the assignment, wrapping up.

This segment is presented to the classroom by means of a PowerPoint presentation.

5. Case pt. 2 (5 minutes)

The case picks up where the assignment and informative segment left. Part 2 of the case is shown to the classroom through a 'motion comic' (a short animated movie, approximately 2 minutes). The case presents a situation in which the central character finds themselves. The case again ends with a problem, dilemma or question (typically: what would you do?)

6. Assignment 2 (10 minutes)

The assignment can take the form of:

A) quiz with closed and open questions, to be answered by the whole classroom

B) open questions and assignments

The quizzes and questions for the assignment are presented to the classroom by means of a PowerPoint presentation.

7. Informative segment (5 minutes)

This segment provides some additional information following the case and the assignment, wrapping up.

8. Optional: in-depth theory (10 minutes)

In case a teacher really wants to challenge the classroom, and has the time to do so, they can present some in-depth theory & questions for discussion.

This segment is presented to the classroom by means of a PowerPoint presentation.

9. General conclusion (5 minutes)

The teacher tells the pupils where they can find more materials if they like: reports, booklets, brochures, films and animations.

Adjusting teaching package to timeslots and levels

In the table below, we suggest how teachers can fit the teaching package to the needs of their specific classroom.

Time available	Content (no.)	Content
30 – 45 minutes	1 – 4 & 9	Case pt. 1 + Assignment 1 (A or B)
60 minutes	1 – 7 & 9	Case pt. 1 & 2 + Assignment 1 (A or B) & 2 (A or B)
Optional	8	In-depth theory (+ optional assignment)

DISTRIBUTION

All the materials will be distributed via the website: <http://beucitizen.eu/teaching-packages/>
The website https://europa.eu/teachers-corner/content/homepage_en links to the materials.

The first part of teaching package 1 will be published on <http://beucitizen.eu/teaching-packages/> as a proof-of-concept / beta version as soon as possible, but no later than April 25.

This proof-of-concept / beta version will be tested in practice with the target group to check whether they find the materials appealing and educational.

The deadline for publishing the final versions of all five teaching packages is July 15.

We aim to make the material as easily accessible and usable in the classroom as possible. We avoided making handouts that need to be printed. There is no need for individual computers for every pupil.

This means the only thing needed in the classroom is:

- A computer with internet connection
- A projector and a screen, or a monitor, connected to the computer
- Speakers connected to the computer to play sound

APPENDIX - LEARNING OBJECTIVE AND CONTENT PER PACKAGE

TEACHING PACKAGE 1 - GETTING MY RIGHTS: EUROPEANIZATION AT HOME

Working title: Boris and his headphones

Main character: Boris

Topic: Consumer rights

Learning objective: raising awareness of how the EU protects consumer rights.

General instruction (5 minutes)

The teacher tells the pupils:

- What topic this lesson will be about.
- What the learning objective is.
- How long the lesson will take and what parts it consists of.

Case pt. 1 (5 minutes) – ‘Reclaiming your money’

“For a long time, Boris has looked forward to this moment. Delivering newspapers every morning, sometimes in the pouring rain. It was all worth it. Finally, his hard work pays off. Today those brand new headphones he ordered will be delivered. Boy, will he be the king of the playground and those new songs coming out, they’ll sound so much better than on his old headphones.

For a while he thought he would never be able to buy the headphones. No matter how long he saved, he never seemed to have enough money. Until one day, browsing on the internet, he found an advertisement. The headphones with 25% discount! He ordered them immediately. They came from a company all the way from another EU country, not from the store at the corner. But hey, that is the way you do shopping nowadays right?

When the bell rings Boris runs to the door, he eagerly grabs the package from the mailman’s hands and opens it. He plugs it in, plays start, and... nothing happens. No matter what Boris tries, the headphones don’t work. They must be broken. Boris is devastated. What can he do?”

Assignment 1 (10 minutes)

A) Quiz

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and the groups answers them as a whole.
Questions:

(Optional introductory question) Have you ever experienced anything like this yourself? What did you do?

1. Do you think it is possible for Boris to reclaim his money?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. What do you think should Boris do to reclaim the money?
 - a. Contact the police
 - b. Contact the mayor
 - c. Contact the company

3. Do you think it would have made a difference if Boris bought the headphones at the shop on the corner of his street?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

B) Open discussion

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and moderates the discussion.

(Optional introductory question) Have you ever experienced anything like this yourself? What did you do?

1. What do you think Boris should do?

2. Why should he do?

3. Do you think it would have made a difference if Boris bought the headphones at the shop on the corner of his street? Why or why not?

Optional to question 1 - 3: search the internet for clues.

Informative segment 1 (5 minutes)

These slides will be designed in the same style as the animated movie.

Slide

Because of European wide agreements, all consumers in the EU are protected by the same rules.

Slide

Under EU rules, a trader must repair, replace, reduce the price or give you a refund if goods you bought turn out to be faulty or do not look or work as advertised.

Slide

If you bought a good or a service online or outside of a shop (by telephone, mail order, from a door-to-door salesperson), you also have the right to cancel and return your order within 14 days, for any reason and with no justification.

Case pt. 2 (5 minutes) – ‘Setting up a web shop yourself’

“Boris contacts the company, and they refund his payment. He is glad that worked out, but he is also disappointed by his experiences with the online web shop. So he heads for the store on the corner of the street. To his surprise, he finds that they are having the exact type of headphones he’s looking for on sale. They are 50% off!

Since they have quite a few of the headphones in stock, a plan comes to mind. He uses the computer programming lessons he learned in school to set up a web shop. With a loan from his uncle he buys a bunch of headphones. Within no time he is selling headphones throughout all corners of the EU. It helps that he isn’t paying any import duty when he ships the headphones to another EU country.

He discovers that he sells more headphones, if he advertises them with a photo in which he photoshopped a famous actor wearing the headphones. One day he receives an angry e-mail from a customer. Boris is puzzled. What could he have done wrong?”

Assignment 2 (10 minutes)

A) Quiz

(Optional introductory question) Have you ever thought about setting up business yourself? What would you sell?

1. Do you think Boris has done something wrong?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. What could he have done wrong?
 - a. Made a false advertisement
 - b. He should have his customers pay import duty
 - c. (Answer tbd)

3. Which other rules do you think the EU has set?
 - a. Uniform phone costs throughout the EU
 - b. The constitution of your country
 - c. (Answer tbd)

B) Open discussion

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and moderates the discussion.

(Optional introductory question) Have you ever thought about setting up business yourself? What would you sell?

1. What do you think Boris could have done wrong?

2. Can you think of 5 other rights you have as a customer in the EU? (take 2 minutes to write them down)

3. [Question/assignment]

Optional to question 1 - 3: search the internet for clues.

Informative segment 2 (5 minutes)

These slides will be designed in the same style as the animated movie.

Slide

Consumers in the EU are protected by a number of other rules, besides the ones we already discussed.

Slide

These rules include unfair pricing, unfair contract terms etc.

Slide

If you think you have been mistreated as a customer, you can do A, B or C.

In-depth theory (10 minutes)

Possible in-depth topics

- What are rights? What are duties? Why do rights and duties always go together?
- Why do you think is it efficient to organize consumer rights EU-wide instead of per country?
- Which institutions can be involved in resolving a customer dispute?

In this block the teacher can use and refer to existing materials.

General conclusion (5 minutes)

The teacher asks the pupils:

- Whether they think they learned something about the EU?
- What they found most surprising or interesting?
- Whether they would like to know more? (and refers them to the places where they can find the information)

References

http://ec.europa.eu/consumers/consumer_rights/index_en.htm

http://europa.eu/youreurope/citizens/consumers/shopping/guarantees-returns/index_en.htm

TEACHING PACKAGE 2 - LOBBYING AND GETTING IN TOUCH WITH THE EU

Working title: Making the future work for us

Main character: Lucie

Topic: Labour market

Learning objective: Understanding different levels of influence and policy making (local, regional, national, European)

General instruction (5 minutes)

The teacher tells the pupils:

- What topic this lesson will be about.
- What the learning objective is.
- How long the lesson will take and what parts it consists of.

Case pt. 1 (5 minutes) – ‘A dream job’

“Lucie is having a discussion in her classroom about work, and what she would like to be later on. Lucie has read about electric cars as being the transportation of the future. She is highly interested in mechanical engineering, and her dream job would be to work at such a factory, but at the moment, there is no factory like that even near her town. The carmaker produces most of its cars in the United States. What can she do?”

Assignment 1 (10 minutes)

A) Quiz

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and the groups answers them as a whole.

(Optional introductory question) What would your dream job be?

Question 1

1. What could be the first step Lucie could take?
2. What could be the second step Lucie could take?
3. What could be the third step Lucie could take?

B) Open discussion

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and moderates the discussion.

(Optional introductory question) What would your dream job be?

Questions 1, 2 and 3

Informative segment (5 minutes)

These slides will be designed in the same style as the animated movie.

Slide

There are several levels at which you can take action: local, regional, national and EU (include figure here).

Case pt. 2 (5 minutes) – ‘A factory for the future’

“Lucie is excited. With her enthusiasm and ability to mobilize others, she effectively did win the local union and the local government for her cause: trying to convince an electric car manufacturer to move a factory to her town.

Now, a delegation of her national government is contacting the EU. The EU could play a decisive part in this stage. When the carmaker produces its cars in the EU, this will have several benefits. The car manufacturer doesn’t need to pay import tariffs when shipping cars within the EU. He can benefit from subsidies on clean technology. So Lucie’s dream job is in sight. What could be her final move?”

Assignment 2 (10 minutes)

Informative segment 2 (5 minutes)

In-depth theory (10 minutes)

General conclusion (5 minutes)

References

TEACHING PACKAGE 3 - ORGANIZING OUR INTEREST

Working title: A multimedia centre in our town

Main character: Juan

Topic: (Popular) culture

Learning objective: Organizing different interests around a common goal.

General instruction (5 minutes)

The teacher tells the pupils:

- What topic this lesson will be about.
- What the learning objective is.
- How long the lesson will take and what parts it consists of.

Case pt. 1 (5 minutes) – ‘A multimedia centre’

“Juan is an avid watcher of vloggers online. And not just of the vloggers who vlog about fashion, lifestyle and make-up. He especially likes the vlogs that explain how complex things work, like School of Life, In a nutshell and the RSA videos. He would also like to be a vlogger or an animator. Or maybe a computer programmer. Unfortunately, at school they don’t these things. Luckily, he discovered an empty building around the corner. That would be a perfect location for a multimedia centre, where he and his friends could playfully learn about all these things. But where should the money come from?”

Assignment 1 (10 minutes)

A) Quiz

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and the groups answers them as a whole.

(Optional introductory question) What would you like to learn, if you could choose from anything?

Question 1, 2 and 3

B) Open discussion

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and moderates the discussion.

(Optional introductory question) What would your dream job be?

Questions 1, 2 and 3

Informative segment (5 minutes)

These slides will be designed in the same style as the animated movie.

Slides

Learning about EU subsidies and how they are distributed.

Case pt. 2 (5 minutes) – ‘Unifying conflicting interests’

“With a little help from his teacher, Juan has managed to find a EU fund which grants subsidies for projects like his. However, some older people in his town have heard about his plans, and they want something else: a place to celebrate the past. Their support is crucial for the subsidy. How can he resolve these conflicting interests?”

Assignment 2 (10 minutes)

Roleplay: dealing with conflicting interests and finding a way to solve them.

Informative segment 2 (5 minutes)

Dealing with conflicting interests and finding a way to solve them.

In case of Juan: the elderly can also use the multimedia centre to watch films about the past.

In-depth theory (10 minutes)

General conclusion (5 minutes)

References

Places to find your way towards EU subsidies.

TEACHING PACKAGE 4 - TRAVELLING AROUND

Working title: A school trip with a twist

Main character: Vanja

Topic: Mobility and travel
(and care/education)

Learning objective: Learning about the rights for EU citizens that come with travelling abroad, education abroad and care abroad.

General instruction (5 minutes)

The teacher tells the pupils:

- What topic this lesson will be about.
- What the learning objective is.
- How long the lesson will take and what parts it consists of.

Case pt. 1 (5 minutes) – ‘A trip with a twist’

“Vanja goes on a school trip. Unfortunately, she falls ill. What now?”

Assignment 1 (10 minutes)

A) Quiz

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and the groups answers them as a whole.

(Optional introductory question) Have you ever been on a school trip abroad? If so, where did you go? If not, where would you like to go? Why?

Questions about your rights to work, travel and receive healthcare in the EU.

B) Open discussion

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and moderates the discussion.

(Optional introductory question) Have you ever been on a school trip abroad? If so, where did you go? If not, where would you like to go? Why?

Questions 1, 2 and 3

Informative segment (5 minutes)

These slides will be designed in the same style as the animated movie.

Slide

Slides about your rights to work, travel and receive healthcare in the EU.

Case pt. 2 (5 minutes) – ‘Studying (and working) abroad’

“Vanja was treated so well in the hospital, that she decides she wants to study medicine in the country she visited. Years after her school trip she goes to study there.”

Assignment 2 (10 minutes)

Informative segment 2 (5 minutes)

In-depth theory (10 minutes)

General conclusion (5 minutes)

References

TEACHING PACKAGE 5 - ADVISING THE EU IN SOLVING GLOBAL PROBLEMS

Working title: Clean air for all of us

Main character: Nikolas

Topic: Environment

Learning objective: Developing negotiation skills.

Understanding that complex issues are dealt with at multiple levels within the EU.

General instruction (5 minutes)

The teacher tells the pupils:

- What topic this lesson will be about.
- What the learning objective is.
- How long the lesson will take and what parts it consists of.

Case pt. 1 (5 minutes) – ‘A dream job’

“Nikolas notices the air in his city is not as clean as it used to be. When he reads a little about this issue, he discovers that it affects a lot of countries, and that pollution in one country also affects the environment in another. On television he has seen that a treaty has been made on reducing the CO₂-emissions to bring climate change to a halt.

What can Nikolas do?”

Assignment 1 (10 minutes)

A) Quiz

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and the groups answers them as a whole.

(Optional introductory question) How do you feel about the environment?

Questions on having influence on EU decision making: how does the EU work, and how can you influence what is happening?

B) Open discussion

The teacher poses these questions to the group, and moderates the discussion.

(Optional introductory question) How do you feel about the environment?

Questions on having influence on EU decision making: how does the EU work, and how can you influence what is happening?

Informative segment (5 minutes)

These slides will be designed in the same style as the animated movie.

Slide

Showing (visually, in a scheme) how a complex issue like climate change works in terms of causes, effects and means to deal with it.

Case pt. 2 (5 minutes) – ‘Resolving different interests’

“His father has a business in refrigerators. He will be directly affected by EU policy.

What do you think Nikolas can do?”

Assignment 2 (10 minutes)

About understanding collective action and dealing with different interests.

Informative segment 2 (5 minutes)

About understanding collective action and dealing with different interests.

In-depth theory (10 minutes)

General conclusion (5 minutes)

References

APPENDIX II: RELEVANT WEBSITE

Websites for teaching materials on the EU

https://europa.eu/teachers-corner/content/homepage_en

EU in general

Europe - A journal for young people: file:///Users/publiccinema/Downloads/NA0414841ENN_002.pdf

EU citizenship

http://europa.eu/youreurope/citizens/index_en.htm

<https://www.consumerclassroom.eu/>

<https://www.consumerclassroom.eu/resources/subject/citizenship>

https://www.consumerclassroom.eu/sites/default/files/attachment/1/2017/03/15/_shopping_kit_v7_dutch_11.pdf

<http://bookshop.europa.eu/en/partners-pbKN0414052/>